

RESILIENCE

Grant Agreement 101079792, RESILIENCE PPP

User Stories Catalogue - 1st Batch

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1 Introduction

RESILIENCE is a European cross-disciplinary research infrastructure for research on religion in all academic fields. It connects research centres, data holders and services distributed all over Europe and creates new instruments and services for the scientific community. Since RESILIENCE prioritises its future users and their needs, WP3 aims to survey the user requirements as comprehensively as possible, so that the RI will offer those services that are requested or envisioned by the community.

This "User Stories Catalogue - 1st Batch" describes the implementation and results of the first three workshops that took place in Sofia (Bulgaria), Ljubljana (Slovenia) and Volos (Greece). In section 2, the user orientation of RESILIENCE is described and the user groups are briefly outlined. Section 3 explains the procedure and method for creating the user stories, in order to present the evaluation of the analysed material and the 1st batch of user stories in section 4. The summary of the results (section 5) identifies the most frequently addressed user requirements by the South-East European researchers with initial conclusions.¹

2 Users

For RESILIENCE its current and future user base drives its development as a research infrastructure: their needs, expertise, and insights determine services and activities. Work Package 3 focuses on users and addresses the need to better analyse users' requirements for RESILIENCE services. To achieve this, WP 3 has identified three objectives: (1) to reach a mutual understanding between the RESILIENCE partners and the future users of the RI platform concerning the importance and added value of the RI, (2) to define the requirements for RESILIENCE services and prioritise them through use cases and user stories, and (3) to identify the potential user profiles and roles that will inform the development of the Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI).²

¹ Workshop in Sofia: February 2023, in Ljubljana: March 2023, in Volos: May 2023.

² See GRANT AGREEMENT, Project: 101079792 — RESILIENCE PPP — HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02, Description of the Action (Part A), Annex 1: Work package WP3 – USERS, p. 8.

2.1 User-Oriented Approach

RESILIENCE creates a European research infrastructure for the study of religions, providing access to relevant digital and physical sources, data and experts for all those users who research and study religions or who wish to inform and educate themselves as actors in the public sphere about religions and the state of research. RESILIENCE follows a strictly user-oriented approach in order to optimally meet this goal.

During the Design Phase, a stakeholder map³ was created to capture the maximum reach of the RESILIENCE infrastructure. Stakeholders were identified in different steps, taking into account the extent of their involvement and their different roles as consumers or producers in the infrastructure, as well as the relationships between them. The stakeholder community of RESILIENCE is composed of ten clusters: researchers, experts, education sector, resource collection managers, public policy sector, religious faith-based actors, funding and co-funding agencies, other RIs, mass media and society.

In the future Implementation Phase, the infrastructure will depend on a broader stakeholder community, in particular funding and co-funding agencies and other RI's.

In the current Preparation Phase, the target groups are those users whose needs and experiences are addressed by RESILIENCE in a narrower sense. These target groups were identified from the broader circle of stakeholders via two innovation workshops in the Design Phase. Four main user groups were identified and defined, which form the starting point for the RESILIENCE user strategy during this phase. They are briefly described as follows.

³ Confidential deliverable D2.3 from the Design Phase — Grant 871127 — RESILIENCE “High-Level User Strategy Report (RESILIENCE_WP2_USR_01.00_FINAL)”, 2.1 Stakeholder Map; Figure 2, p. 6–8.

2.2 User Groups

In the Design Phase, RESILIENCE explored the different stakeholder groups via innovation workshops, online meetings and surveys, prioritising users and their most important needs.⁴ The user analysis resulted in four main user groups that will benefit most from RESILIENCE:

1. RESILIENCE for Researchers and Experts on Religion

Researchers and experts on religion in all academic fields and related positions (e.g. in governmental research, think tanks etc.) benefit from the RESILIENCE platform with data and contacts. They gain access to more resources, improve their digital skills, build and expand their professional network and can participate in networks and projects that foster research and collaboration.

2. RESILIENCE for Collection Managers and Librarians (GLAM sector)

Collection managers and librarians benefit from access to tools and services tailored to their needs, as well as training courses. The RI offers them expert advice and support for new developments, especially in the field of Digital Humanities. The platform offered by RESILIENCE will help to disseminate unique and valuable collections, improve digital and physical access for users, and increase engagement with collections – necessary to secure sustainable funding.

3. RESILIENCE for the Political Sphere

RESILIENCE provides political actors with access to informed and data-driven research on all aspects of religion: historical context, socio-political research, anthropological perspectives, and cutting edge research on the impact of religion on society. Research outcomes are thus made usable for their work in practice.

⁴ Confidential deliverable D2.3 from the Design Phase — Grant 871127 — RESILIENCE “High-Level User Strategy Report (RESILIENCE_WP2_USR_01.00_FINAL)”, 2.2 Defining and Analysing the Targeted User Group, p. 8–12.

4. RESILIENCE for the Religious Communities

RESILIENCE enables religious communities to access in-depth information and research results in their field. It facilitates networking between research and religious communities, which enrich each other through the exchange of data and knowledge.

Of these four user groups, researchers form the main user group of research infrastructures and have the highest priority.⁵ It was therefore the obvious choice to start the survey of user needs with this key user group of researchers on religion in all academic fields. In the third workshop, this future user group was complemented by the expertise of the second user group, librarians and collection managers.

2.3 User Stories

The user stories are created to identify potential user profiles, define and prioritise RESILIENCE services in cooperation with WP2 and find a synergy with both the research community on religion and the broader RI landscape. This first batch of user stories (D3.5), which are presented in this document, comes from the three workshops that WP3 held together with the partners from the consortium (mainly WP2 and WP4). Since one of RESILIENCE's strategies is to make the RI better known in Eastern Europe and the Balkans,⁶ it was appropriate to hold the first three workshops in this region. This geographical focus will allow comparisons between different regions and a targeted strategy for Eastern Europe and the Balkans in the further progression of the project. The interviews (description under 3. Methodology) took place in Sofia (Bulgaria) at the Centre for Slavo-

⁵ See CLARIN's "[Value Proposition 2021](#)" and DARIAH's "[Strategic Plan 2019–2026](#)", which clearly prioritise the needs of researchers, while also addressing further user groups in politics and society.

⁶ See GRANT AGREEMENT, Project: 101079792 — RESILIENCE PPP — HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02, Annex 1, Description of the Action (Part B): 2.2 Measures to maximise impact – Dissemination, exploitation and communication, c) Definition of strategies, p. 12.

Byzantine Studies "Prof. Ivan Dujčev", at the Catholic Theological Faculty of the University of Ljubljana (Slovenia) and in Volos (Greece) at the Volos Academy for Theological Studies, specialising in the history and theology of contemporary Eastern Orthodox Christianity, and in ecumenical and interreligious dialogue.

3 Methodology

To gain a better understanding of the user requirements, the workshops are organised to ask in detail about the needs of the users of an RI for religion in all academic fields, not only to understand the needs of the users, but more importantly to learn what their priorities are and to guide the development of the services accordingly.⁷

3.1 The Development of the Joint Workshop "RESILIENCE Meets Researchers"

WP3 decided to use a qualitative empirical approach through the conduction of interviews with researchers in different contexts, which were selected to allow a representative data collection. This concept was tested in advance in trial-runs with researchers at the Faculty of Protestant Theology at the University of Münster. A semi-structured guide for interviewing the selected focus groups was designed by WP3 to standardise the approach and receive valid and comparable information. It was embedded in a workshop concept – called "RESILIENCE meets Researchers" – which was tested in different contexts (a more detailed description of the approach and the workshops' proceedings will be presented in D3.1). The guideline for the workshops is a living document and is open to relevant adjustments based on the feedback given by participants and the interviewers as well as the acquirement of expertise and more detailed insights, which are

⁷ See GRANT AGREEMENT, Project: 101079792 — RESILIENCE PPP — HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02, Annex 1, Description of the Action (Part A): Work package WP3 – USERS, p. 8.

gained through the analysis of the interviews. However, changes should not be fundamental, so the comparability of the interview situations is not jeopardised.

The process of data collection is divided into two phases. In the first phase, the participants are asked in so-called guided or expert interviews about the research infrastructures available to them, their experiences with them and the possibilities of a new RI.

In the second phase, the participants are invited to a group discussion in which the synergy effects of a group dynamic are used to create a discussion of the possibilities, advantages and added value of a European research infrastructure for their research. The collected user stories can be converted into user requirements through the content analysis of the conducted interviews. These can thereafter be transformed into inputs for prioritisation of services by WP2.

3.2 Qualitative Content Analysis

Within the scope of empirical social research, the WP decided to use qualitative content analysis for the data analysis of the interviews. Qualitative content analysis is the most applicable method for texts that are produced during data collection within the framework of social science research projects, e.g. – as in our case – transcripts of interviews. The basis for the evaluation process is the analysis process model according to Philipp Mayring.⁸ This approach was chosen because it is both rule-based and flexible, and because it creates the possibility of integrating inductive and deductive category formation. An inductive procedure offers the possibility to answer explorative, theory-generating questions. A deductive procedure on the other hand, allows more concrete and theory-guided questions. In this way, it was possible to use the guideline of the individual interviews as the basis for coding, which was then enriched through the deductive addition of codes through the detailed analysis of the transcribed material (for a more detailed description see 3.4 Coding of Interview Transcripts). The following figure illustrates the workflow of the qualitative content analysis used in this context:

⁸ Cf. Mayring, Philipp: Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse. Grundlagen und Techniken, Beltz: Weinheim 2022.

Figure 1: Workflow for Qualitative Content Analysis

3.3 Analysed Material

As material for the qualitative content analysis, 23 transcribed individual interviews and four group interviews were available. These interviews were transcribed and proofread in a standardised way. The anonymised transcripts can be found on the G-Drive of the RESILIENCE consortium. These transcripts then formed the basis for the coding, which was carried out with the programme MAXQDA.

The average duration of the individual interviews was 51 minutes, while the average duration of the group interviews was 60 minutes. The workshops took place in three countries, with scholars from ten institutions out of eight different academic disciplines on religion (philosophy, theology, biblical studies, history, anthropology, psychology, Islamic studies, philology) and librarians from two libraries who could be interviewed. Among those interviewed were MSc students, PhD candidates, doctors and professors. The gender ratio was 10 women, 13 men, 0 divers. The age of the interviewees ranged from 22 to 63 years.

3.4 Coding of Interview Transcripts

Coding interviews is an essential method of qualitative data analysis which allows to gain deeper insights into the data collected. WP3 systematically assigned codes to relevant themes and patterns in order to structure and analyse the complex and extensive information produced via the interviews. Coding is therefore a crucial step in gaining meaningful and valid insights about user needs. Additionally, the systematic approach through coding the interviews can lead to a clearer insight and make the results more comprehensible.

As mentioned above, the two possible ways to code the qualitative data were applied: inductive and deductive. By using the questions that led to the creation of the semi-structured interview guide, some preliminary coding categories were already available to search for in the interview data. This deductive coding approach thus also assesses our pre-assumed foci. These key elements were:

- Research Data/Research Data Management
- Software/Tools
- Digital Humanities
- Networking/Mobility/Transnational Access Programme
- Digital Research Infrastructure

Other coding categories were added after reviewing the transcripts. By identifying themes, inductive coding was used. These were the following:

- Enhancement of Research and the field of Religious Studies
- Data exchange
- Keeping updated
- User friendliness
- Translation obstacles
- Funding
- Scientific support/Empowerment
- Training
- Quality control/Peer Review/Feedback
- Accessibility

The different codes vary in their characteristics and differ in their concreteness and abstractness. The majority of the statements could be assigned to one particular code and in some cases they matched more than one, so that different allocations were applied. With these results, a first prioritisation of the expectations and wishes of the future users for the RESILIENCE RI can be derived (see 4.1, 4.2).

4 Results

Through the analysis of the interviews, i.e. the user-centred conversation, the coding and the resulting prioritisation of the needs, the foundation for the user stories is laid. Since a user story describes a certain functionality, their goal is to obtain a shared understanding of the user needs and the future RESILIENCE services that will be derived from those needs. In addition, these short, concise statements can also be helpful in communicating the goals of the RI.

4.1 Prioritisation

The coding that has been carried out is used to prioritise the specified focal points regarding the wishes and needs of the future users. This prioritisation then serves as the basis for creating the user stories. The numbers in the following chart are the result of the frequency of mentions. This means the total sum of the statements made, which were coded under the respective term.

Figure 2: Code System Statistics

4.2 User Stories 1st Batch

The following user stories were extracted from the statements of the 23 individual interviews and the four group interviews. They were combined or merged in terms of content with regard to the top statements. Depending on the range of user needs expressed, two or more user stories were identified. The user stories collected here show the different user roles targeting specific RI services. The form used is: "As a <role>, I want <capability>, so that <benefit>."

Accessibility (15% - 88 statements)

As a researcher, I want a wide range of access to digitised literature, so that the scope of my research is not reduced by a lack of travel options.

As a researcher, I want some kind of document issued by RESILIENCE, that allows me to access libraries and catalogues throughout Europe, so that I am not restricted in my research.

Networking/Mobility/Transnational Access (TNA) (14% - 80 statements)

As a researcher, I want to have a centralised register of researchers and their expertise, so I can contact people who can enrich my research.

As a researcher, I want to have a contact person at the place I am visiting, so I can get instructed on the use of libraries, catalogues etc.

Research Data Management (10% - 60 statements)

As a researcher, I want my data to be sustainably stored, so it stays available and usable after the finalisation of a project.

As a researcher, I want to have a central data repository to ensure secure data storage.

Software/Tools (10% - 59 statements)

As a researcher, I want to be able to customise my search results, so that they fit my research.

As a researcher, I want a reliable translation tool, to expand my opportunities regarding the choice of research literature.

Enhancement of Research and the field of Religious Studies (9% - 51 statements)

As a librarian, I want a Research Infrastructure that provides me with high-end data and solutions, so I can offer my support to researchers and enhance the research in Religious Studies.

Scientific support/Empowerment (8% - 49 statements)

As an early career researcher, I want RESILIENCE to be an agent for personal mentoring, so I can get in touch with experts in my field.

As a collection manager, I want to have content-related support by experts in the field of Religious Studies, so that I can optimise the standard and variety of our collection.

Digital Research Infrastructure (7% - 39 statements)

As a librarian, I want a Digital Research Infrastructure that unites different library catalogues in an overarching system, so that the librarians are connected and can assist each other.

As a researcher, I want to have a single access platform, so that I can work more efficiently.

Data exchange (6% - 37 statements)

As a researcher, I want a digital marketplace to get in touch with people working on the same subject, to exchange data and experience.

Funding (5% - 26 statements)

As a researcher, I want RESILIENCE to cultivate relationships with the government and society to stress the importance of Religious Studies, so that the funding for research can be sufficient.

User friendliness (4% - 23 statements)

As a researcher, I want a single access point with a user interface, which is simple and user friendly, to save time during my research.

As a user of a Research Infrastructure, I want a Help Desk, so I can be directed to the tools and data that are a perfect fit for my individual research.

Training (4% - 23 statements)

As a Ph.D. student, I want to be trained in searching data more effectively, so I can work more efficiently.

As a collection manager, I want to be trained in the digitisation of rare manuscripts, so I can enrich our collection with this data.

Translation obstacles (3% - 19 statements)

As a researcher, I need a translation tool for specific vocabulary in Religious Studies, so that materials in old and less common languages are understood.

Quality control/Peer Review/Feedback (2% - 10 statements)

As a researcher, I want to participate in a large interdisciplinary network of users, so that I can receive fast and efficient feedback to my planned publications.

As a researcher, I want a platform that is not completely free from review and quality control, so I know the data I am accessing through it is of a certain standard.

Keeping updated (1% - 8 statements)

As a researcher, I want to be part of a digital community, which keeps me reliably informed on conferences, publications, workshops, career opportunities etc., so I can stay updated.

Digital Humanities (1% - 5 statements)

As a researcher, I want a good exchange of ideas with DH, to enrich our take on Religious Studies.

5 Summary and First Implications

The interviewed researchers and librarians have a variety of user needs, which are vividly presented in user stories (4.2). As not all user needs can be met ad hoc in the form of offered services, the user needs have to be prioritised. The analysis of the interviews reveal clearly the main concerns of the potential users of RESILIENCE: two user needs can be identified that clearly stand out quantitatively from the others:

With 88 hits, the keyword "accessibility" is the most prominent user need among South-Eastern European users of RESILIENCE. From the interviews it is evident that the keyword "accessibility" refers in particular to literature. If RESILIENCE wants to make a significant contribution to researchers in South-Eastern Europe, it must be examined whether and how we can meet this user need.

The keyword "network/ing" also stands out significantly from the other keywords (14%/80 statements). Researchers from South-Eastern Europe see great value in the networking of researchers. The interviews show that the desire for academic exchange must not fail because of the finances for travel expenses. The majority of interviewees affirmed the statement "connection is key" and elaborated on how much they depend on exchange in their work. A free platform on which this would be made possible meets the user needs of South-Eastern European researchers.

With the 1st batch of user stories, WP3 contributes a first crucial building block for a precise analysis of the needs of potential users. However, in order to obtain a comprehensive picture of user needs, it is necessary to organise further surveys at other locations in Europe. The results of these future surveys will be used to generate a comprehensive image of user needs.

6 Reference Documents

Reference documents are intended to provide background and supplementary information.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
R1	18/08/2022	GRANT AGREEMENT, Project: 101079792 — RESILIENCE PPP — HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02
R2	31/08/2020	D2.3: High-Level User Strategy Report — Grant 871127 — RESILIENCE (RESILIENCE_WP2_USR_01.00_FINAL) [Confidential]

Annex: A) Guideline Interview, B) Group Discussion

RESILIENCE Meets Researchers in Bulgaria

**Discussing Needs, Experiences,
Requirements**

A) Guideline Interview

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1.1 General information

In the guided interview, a partially or fully standardized questionnaire is replaced by an interview guideline that contains the topics and aspects of topics to be covered with suggested questions. The aim of such an interview is to generate area-specific and object-related statements. The duration of a guideline or expert interview should not exceed one hour. The interviewing person should be a competent listener. He/she is not constrained by a standardized questionnaire but must be able to react flexibly to the interview situation and the answer of the interviewed person. The interpreting ability of the interviewing person is not only important for the evaluation, but also with regard to appropriate follow-up questions during the interview. The interviewing person should be empathetic and open but also critical for appropriate follow-up questions.

1.2 Information about the guideline

The 'user requirements' workshop is based on a semi-structured guideline. On the one hand, this kind of template offers the interviewing person openness and freedom to go into the answers and topics addressed by the participant. On the other hand, the interviewing person is provided with a structure, topics and guiding questions so that the interview results of various user requirements workshops can be compared with each other in a valid way.

The goal of the guided interviews is to capture the research situation of the participants, as well as their requirements related to a future RI (RESILIENCE).

The interview guideline is structured by its underlying themes: The researcher's situation will be assessed based on his/her 1) experience in and use of research data and way of research data management, 2) experience in and use of digital tools and instruments, 3) experience and possibilities of networking, 4) experience with and use of already existing research infrastructures. At the end of the interview the interviewee is invited to participate in a thought experiment. In this, they are encouraged to think about the future of their research as well as the added value of RESILIENCE.

Three different types of questions are assigned to each of the above mentioned themes. With an introductory question, the interviewer can introduce the interviewee to the topic and lead to the more detailed questions. Specifying questions provide the interviewer with sample questions that allow him or her to ask more about the topic being addressed. Also, they can be used to keep the flow of the interview and keep the interviewee interested in talking about his/her opinions and experiences. The key questions each provide an outlook on the topic of RESILIENCE. Here, the interview situation must be well observed by the interviewer, so that the key question is asked at an appropriate point and does not interrupt the conversation unnaturally.

1.3 Preparation

As an interviewing person you will receive some basic information about your interviewee, who was asked to provide these information before the interview. Make sure to keep these basic information in mind. It will help you through the interview. You will be equipped with a recording device. Make yourself familiar with this kind of device, so there won't be any technical issues during the interview. Equip yourself with a glass of water for your interviewee and yourself. Read carefully through the guideline and make sure you know the different topics by heart.

1.4 Implementation

Before starting the interview make sure the recording device is recording. Kindly welcome your interviewee and start the conversation. After you have talked about the user requirements express gratitude for attending this conversation.

1.5 Postprocessing

After the interview, take 5 min to reflect on the conversation. These questions may help you:

- What was the most important impetus from the conversation?
- On which topic did the conversation go smoothly?
- When did the conversation falter?
- How did you feel in your role as an interviewing person?

1.6 Helpful advice

- Make sure your language is simple and jargon-free. Be friendly: smile, make eye contact with participants, speak in a pleasant tone of voice, use relaxed body language, incorporate humour where appropriate, be patient and do not rush participants to respond.
- Do not speak too much – focus on asking questions and make sure that every participant is able to share their thoughts.
- When the participants are silent after you have asked a question, do not take it as an answer. You have to ask additional questions (maybe you have not been understood properly, or they need to get some sense of the direction of your question).
- When someone shares doubts about the idea of the discussed problem of the RI, absolutely do not defend the RI, but simply ask further questions.
- Don't ask more than one question at a time, even if the questions go together.
- All questions should be open-ended.
- Probing is essential for digging deeper to find true meaning. This might include playing back what you've heard from your interviewee.

1.7 Guideline

Topic	Key Question	Introductory Question	Specification Question
<i>Introduction to the person's research</i>			
		Can you tell us what your research is about?	
			Can you please elaborate on this?

Research Data			
		What kind of data are part of your research?	
			To what extent have you dealt with the topic "research data"?
			How do you collect them?
			Did you collect all the data yourself?
			Did you have the possibility to access data from other researchers in their research area?
			What was your experience overall?
Research Data Management			
		How and where do you store your data?	
			Which experiences have you had?
		Which external research data do you use?	

	How would your research benefit if you could enter your data on a Europe-wide repository and access research data of other researchers		Can you elaborate on that?
Software/ Tools/Digital Humanities			
		What technical and/or digital tools do you use?	
			How do they function?
			Was this the only tool that was available to you?
			Which aspects motivated your decision?
	How would your research change, if you were to work with the possibilities in the DH area of other institutes and universities?		
			Could you name some of those, which are of interest to you?

<i>Networking</i>			
		<p>What do you think about the statement: Connection is key? There is a high added value for all researchers if they network with each other."</p>	
			<p>How would you describe your own research network? How did this come about? Institutions / Researchers</p>
		<p>What kind of experience do you have with research stays at other universities and institutions?</p>	
			<p>Would you like to see a broader offer of exchange programs?</p>
			<p>What kind of services or sources would you prioritize in choosing a location for a research visit? What would make you want to apply for a stay?</p>
		<p>To what extent is funding important to you in applying for an external research visit?</p>	

	To what extent could a centrally organized networking facility of researchers and institutes add value to your research? Think about online platforms, network programs, congresses etc.		
Digital Research Infrastructure			
		What experience do you have with digital research infrastructure so far?	
			How did these influence your research?
Outlook			
		How do you envision working in your research area in 10 years ?	

Please imagine:
A multitude of European universities establish a pan-European research infrastructure in the field of RS, in order to make the expertise/data available beyond the boundaries of their own institutions, to create specialized repositories for the different areas of RS, and to build a relationship between institutes.
In which way would the use of this infrastructure have an impact on your work?

1.8 Notes

RESILIENCE Meets Researchers in Bulgaria

**Discussing Needs, Experiences,
Requirements**

B) Group Discussion

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1.1 General Information

In the group discussion, a moderator presents a topic to a group for discussion and encourages participants to express their opinion and to discuss it with the other participants. Another very important person in this process is the assistant, who is taking minutes. The recording and the minutes will later be complemented by the notes taken by the interviewed people on index cards, to gain deeper insights in their needs and in obstacles regarding those.

At best, the group dynamic ensures that the participants encourage each other to express their opinions in more detail than in an individual interview. The group size varies between six and ten group members.

1.2 The Task of the Moderator

Regarding the role of the moderator, it is to notice, that it is ambivalent. He or she must motivate the communication, guide the group and its conversation, participate in as well as observe it, but not become too actively involved in the conversation. The Moderator will explain the use of the index cards and then pose the introducing question to the group, which is **“What does good Research mean to you?”** The moderator will try to let the group engage in a discussion about their needs and wishes for their research and will lead them to a future perspective. Furthermore, the moderator has the values, vision, and possibilities of RESILIENCE in mind and tries to connect those to the aspects mentioned in the discussion.

1.3 The Goal of the Discussion

The group discussion aims to gain deeper insights in the user requirements and with that the opportunities of RESILIENCE RI s services. The goal is to explore the added value of RESILIENCE in “good research” as defined by the users. By asking about optimal research conditions, needs can be indirectly uncovered for RESILIENCE to focus on.

1.4 Different Situation

Usually the group discussion is a continuation of an expert interview. However this context is different, the group discussion will be a helpful instrument to get some usable data for the user needs of RESILIENCE. Usually the expert interview gives the opportunity to the researcher to talk about his/her research and their needs regarding research infrastructure (RI) issues. So not having an expert interview before, it could be helpful to not start with the proposed question, but let the participants express their situation of their „daily business“ and about the challenges they face. After that you could come up with questions which are connected to RI: (Data) „What kind of data is part of your research?“, „How and where do you store your data?“, „How would your research benefit if you could enter your data on a Europe-wide repository and access research data of other researchers?“ — (DH) „What technical and/or digital tools do you use?“, „How would your research change, if you were able to work with the possibilities in the DH area of other institutes and universities?“ — (Digital Research Infrastructure) „What experience do you have with digital research infrastructure so far?“, „Please imagine: A multitude of European universities establish a pan-European research infrastructure in the field of religious studies (RS), in order to make the expertise/data available beyond the boundaries of their own institutions, to create specialized repositories for the different areas of RS, and to build a relationship between institutes. In which way would the use of this infrastructure have an impact on your work?“

Another opportunity is to raise a topic, which was already mentioned during the day, regarding to needs of researchers.

Time	Duration	Who	What	Description	Needs
00:00	00:05	Interviewees, Assistant, Moderator	Introduction of participants		Recording device
00:05	00:03	Assistant	Handing out the index cards	At the beginning, the application is not yet directly discussed, but het cards are initially	Index Card, a pen for each participant
00:08	00:03	Moderator	Introduction of further proceeding	<p>The moderator will let the group know of the further proceedings i.e.:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The index cards should be used to record their thoughts in writing on the aspects <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) what would I wish for/ dream of in regard to my research, if money or other resources would not matter? (Green) b) what are issues, what do I see in a critic view? What could be problems? (Red) c) what is realistic? <p>This can happen during or after the discussion. (Blue)</p> <p>The Interviewees can write their thoughts during the discussion or in a short time afterwards. The Moderator explains further that they will start with the topic "What does good Research mean you?" and the discussion will then develop from thereon.</p>	

00:11	00:30	Moderator and participants	Discussion		
00:41	00:04	Moderator	End of discussion	The moderator invites the participants to finalize their thought on the 3 questions regarding their research	
00:45	00:01	Moderator, Assistant	Thanks, Goodbye and collecting index cards		

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